

Direct and Inverse Estimates For Combinations of Bernstein Polynomials with Endpoint Singularities

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Abstract. We give direct and inverse theorems for the weighted approximation of functions with endpoint singularities by combinations of Bernstein polynomials by the r th Ditzian-Totik modulus of smoothness $\omega_{\phi}^r(f, t)_w$ where ϕ is an admissible step-weight function.

Key words and phrases. Bernstein polynomials; Endpoint singularities; Pointwise approximation; Direct and inverse theorems.

1. Introduction

The set of all continuous functions, defined on the interval I , is denoted by $C(I)$. For any $f \in C([0, 1])$, the corresponding Bernstein operators are defined as follows:

$$B_n(f, x) := \sum_{k=0}^n f\left(\frac{k}{n}\right) p_{n,k}(x),$$

Where

$$p_{n,k}(x) := \binom{n}{k} x^k (1-x)^{n-k}, \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n, \quad x \in [0, 1].$$

Approximation properties of Bernstein operators have been studied very well (see [2], [4], [5]-[9], [14]-[16], for example). In order to approximate the functions with singularities, Della Vecchia et al. [4] and Yu-Zhao [14] introduced some kinds of *modified Bernstein operators*. Throughout the paper, C denotes a positive constant independent of n and x , which may be different in different cases.

Ditzian and Totik [5] extended the method of combinations and defined the following combinations of Bernstein operators:

$$B_{n,r}(f, x) := \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} C_i(n) B_{n_i}(f, x),$$

with the conditions:

- (a) $n = n_0 < n_1 < \dots < n_{r-1} \leq Cn$,
- (b) $\sum_{i=0}^{r-1} |C_i(n)| \leq C$,
- (c) $\sum_{i=0}^{r-1} C_i(n) = 1$,
- (d) $\sum_{i=0}^{r-1} C_i(n)n_i^{-k} = 0$, for $k = 1, \dots, r - 1$.

Now, we can define our new combinations of Bernstein operators as follows:

$$(1.1) \quad B_{n,r}^*(f, x) := B_{n,r}(F_n, x) = \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} C_i(n)B_{n_i}(F_n, x),$$

where $C_i(n)$ satisfy the conditions (a)-(d). For the details, it can be referred to [13].

Let $\varphi(x) = \sqrt{x(1-x)}$ and let $\phi : [0, 1] \rightarrow R$, $\phi \neq 0$ be an admissible step-weight function of the Ditzian-Totik modulus of smoothness, that is, ϕ satisfies the following conditions:

- (I) For every proper subinterval $[a, b] \subseteq [0, 1]$ there exists a constant $M_1 \equiv M(a, b) > 0$ Such that $M_1^{-1} \leq \phi(x) \leq M_1$ for $x \in [a, b]$.
- (II) There are two numbers $\beta(0) \geq 0$ and $\beta(1) \geq 0$ for which

$$\phi(x) \sim \begin{cases} x^{\beta(0)}, & \text{as } x \rightarrow 0+, \\ (1-x)^{\beta(1)}, & \text{as } x \rightarrow 1-. \end{cases}$$

($X \sim Y$ which means $C^{-1}Y \leq X \leq CY$ for some C).

Combining condition (I) and (II) on ϕ ; we can deduce that

$$M^{-1}\phi_2(x) \leq \phi(x) \leq M\phi_2(x), x \in [0, 1],$$

Where $\phi_2(x) = x^{\beta(0)}(1-x)^{\beta(1)}$, and M is a positive constant independent of x .

Let

$$w(x) = x^\alpha(1-x)^\beta, \alpha, \beta \geq 0, \alpha + \beta > 0, 0 \leq x \leq 1.$$

and

$$C_w := \{f \in C((0, 1)) : \lim_{x \rightarrow 1} (wf)(x) = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} (wf)(x) = 0\}.$$

The norm in C_w is defined by $\|wf\|_{C_w} := \|wf\| = \sup_{0 \leq x \leq 1} |(wf)(x)|$. Define

$$W_\phi^r := \{f \in C_w : f^{(r-1)} \in A.C.((0, 1)), \|w\phi^r f^{(r)}\| < \infty\},$$

$$W_{\phi,\lambda}^r := \{f \in C_w : f^{(r-1)} \in A.C.((0, 1)), \|w\phi^{r\lambda} f^{(r)}\| < \infty\}.$$

For $f \in C_w$, define the weighted modulus of smoothness by

$$\omega_{\phi}^r(f, t)_w := \sup_{0 < h \leq t} \{ \|w \Delta_{h\phi}^r f\|_{[16h^2, 1-16h^2]} + \|w \overrightarrow{\Delta}_h^r f\|_{[0, 16h^2]} + \|w \overleftarrow{\Delta}_h^r f\|_{[1-16h^2, 1]} \},$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_{h\phi}^r f(x) &= \sum_{k=0}^r (-1)^k \binom{r}{k} f(x + (\frac{r}{2} - k)h\phi(x)), \\ \overrightarrow{\Delta}_h^r f(x) &= \sum_{k=0}^r (-1)^k \binom{r}{k} f(x + (r - k)h), \\ \overleftarrow{\Delta}_h^r f(x) &= \sum_{k=0}^r (-1)^k \binom{r}{k} f(x - kh). \end{aligned}$$

Recently Felten showed the following two theorems in [6]:

Theorem A. Let $\varphi(x) = \sqrt{x(1-x)}$ and let $\phi : [0, 1] \rightarrow R$, $\phi \neq 0$ be an admissible step-weight function of the Ditzian-Totik modulus of smoothness([5]) such that ϕ^2 and φ^2/ϕ^2 are concave. Then, for $f \in C[0, 1]$ and $0 < \alpha < 2$, $|B_n(f, x) - f(x)| \leq \omega_{\phi}^2(f, n^{-1/2} \frac{\varphi(x)}{\phi(x)})$.

Theorem B. Let $\varphi(x) = \sqrt{x(1-x)}$ and let $\phi : [0, 1] \rightarrow R$, $\phi \neq 0$ be an admissible step-weight function of the Ditzian-Totik modulus of smoothness([5]) such that ϕ^2 and φ^2/ϕ^2 are concave. Then, for $f \in C[0, 1]$ and $0 < \alpha < 2$, $|B_n(f, x) - f(x)| = O((n^{-1/2} \frac{\varphi(x)}{\phi(x)})^\alpha)$ implies $\omega_{\phi}^2(f, t) = O(t^\alpha)$.

Our main results are the following:

Theorem 2.1. For any $\alpha, \beta > 0$, $\min\{\beta(0), \beta(1)\} \geq \frac{1}{2}$, $f \in C_w$, we have

$$(2.1) \quad |w(x)\phi^r(x)B_{n,r-1}^{*(r)}(f, x)| \leq Cn^{\frac{\alpha}{2}} \|wf\|.$$

Theorem 2.2. For any $\alpha, \beta > 0$, $f \in W_{\phi}^r$, we have

$$(2.2) \quad |w(x)\phi^r(x)B_{n,r-1}^{*(r)}(f, x)| \leq C \|w\phi^r f^{(r)}\|.$$

Theorem 2.3. For $f \in C_w$, $\alpha, \beta > 0$, $\min\{\beta(0), \beta(1)\} \geq \frac{1}{2}$, we have

$$(2.3) \quad w(x)|f(x) - B_{n,r-1}^{*(r)}(f, x)| = O((n^{-\frac{1}{2}}\phi^{-1}(x)\delta_n(x))^{\alpha_0}) \iff \omega_{\phi}^r(f, t)_w = O(t^{\alpha_0}),$$

where $\alpha_0 \in (0, r)$.

3. LEMMAS

Lemma 3.1. ([15]) For any non-negative real u and v , we have

$$(3.1) \quad \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \left(\frac{k}{n}\right)^{-u} \left(1 - \frac{k}{n}\right)^{-v} p_{n,k}(x) \leq Cx^{-u}(1-x)^{-v}.$$

Lemma 3.2. ([4]) If $\gamma \in \mathbb{R}$, then

$$(3.2) \quad \sum_{k=0}^n |k - nx|^\gamma p_{n,k}(x) \leq C n^{\frac{\gamma}{2}} \varphi^\gamma(x).$$

Lemma 3.3. For any $f \in W_{\phi}^r$, $\alpha, \beta > 0$, we have

$$(3.3) \quad \|w\phi^r F_n^{(r)}\| \leq C \|w\phi^r f^{(r)}\|.$$

Proof. By symmetry, we only prove the above result when $x \in (0, 1/2]$, the others can be done similarly. Obviously, when $x \in (0, 1/n]$, by [5], we have

$$\begin{aligned} |L_r^{(r)}(f, x)| &\leq C |\vec{\Delta}_{\frac{1}{r}} f(0)| \leq C n^{-\frac{r}{2}+1} \int_0^{\frac{x}{n}} u^{\frac{r}{2}} |f^{(r)}(u)| du \\ &\leq C n^{-\frac{r}{2}+1} \|w\phi^r f^{(r)}\| \int_0^{\frac{x}{n}} u^{\frac{r}{2}} w^{-1}(u) \phi^{-r}(u) du. \end{aligned}$$

So

$$|w(x)\phi^r(x)F_n^{(r)}(x)| \leq C \|w\phi^r f^{(r)}\|.$$

If $x \in [\frac{1}{n}, \frac{2}{n}]$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |w(x)\phi^r(x)F_n^{(r)}(x)| &\leq |w(x)\phi^r(x)f^{(r)}(x)| + |w(x)\phi^r(x)(f(x) - F_n(x))^{(r)}| \\ &:= I_1 + I_2. \end{aligned}$$

For I_2 , we have

$$\begin{aligned} f(x) - F_n(x) &= (\psi(nx - 1) + 1)(f(x) - L_r(f, x)). \\ w(x)\phi^r(x)|(f(x) - F_n(x))^{(r)}| &= w(x)\phi^r(x) \sum_{i=0}^r n^i |f(x) - L_r(f, x)|^{(r-i)}. \end{aligned}$$

By [5], then

$$|(f(x) - L_r(f, x))^{(r-i)}|_{[\frac{1}{n}, \frac{2}{n}]} \leq C(n^{r-i} \|f - L_r\|_{[\frac{1}{n}, \frac{2}{n}]} + n^{-i} \|f^{(r)}\|_{[\frac{1}{n}, \frac{2}{n}]}), \quad 0 < j < r.$$

Now, we estimate

$$(3.4) \quad I := w(x)\phi^r(x)|f(x) - L_r(x)|.$$

By Taylor expansion, we have

$$(3.5) \quad f\left(\frac{i}{n}\right) = \sum_{u=0}^{r-1} \frac{\left(\frac{i}{n} - x\right)^u}{u!} f^{(u)}(x) + \frac{1}{(r-1)!} \int_x^{\frac{i}{n}} \left(\frac{i}{n} - s\right)^{r-1} f^{(r)}(s) ds,$$

It follows from (3.5) and the identities

$$\sum_{i=1}^r \left(\frac{i}{n}\right)^v l_i(x) = Cx^v, \quad v = 0, 1, \dots, r.$$

We have

$$\begin{aligned} L_r(f, x) &= \sum_{i=1}^r \sum_{u=0}^{r-1} \frac{\left(\frac{i}{n} - x\right)^u}{u!} f^{(u)}(x) l_i(x) + \frac{1}{(r-1)!} \sum_{i=1}^r l_i(x) \int_x^{\frac{i}{n}} \left(\frac{i}{n} - s\right)^{r-1} f^{(r)}(s) ds \\ &= f(x) + \sum_{u=1}^{r-1} f^{(u)}(x) \left(\sum_{v=0}^u C_u^v (-x)^{u-v} \sum_{i=1}^r \left(\frac{i}{n}\right)^v l_i(x) \right) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{(r-1)!} \sum_{i=1}^r l_i(x) \int_x^{\frac{i}{n}} \left(\frac{i}{n} - s\right)^{r-1} f^{(r)}(s) ds, \end{aligned}$$

Which implies that

$$w(x)\phi^r(x)|f(x) - L_r(f, x)| = \frac{1}{(r-1)!} w(x)\phi^r(x) \sum_{i=1}^r l_i(x) \int_x^{\frac{i}{n}} \left(\frac{i}{n} - s\right)^{r-1} f^{(r)}(s) ds,$$

Since $|l_i(x)| \leq C$ for $x \in [0, \frac{2}{n}]$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, r$.

It follows from $\frac{|\frac{i}{n} - s|^{r-1}}{w(s)} \leq \frac{|\frac{i}{n} - x|^{r-1}}{w(x)}$, s between $\frac{i}{n}$ and x , then

$$\begin{aligned} w(x)\phi^r(x)|f(x) - L_r(f, x)| &\leq Cw(x)\phi^r(x) \sum_{i=1}^r \int_x^{\frac{i}{n}} \left(\frac{i}{n} - s\right)^{r-1} |f^{(r)}(s)| ds \\ &\leq C\phi^r(x) \|w\phi^r f^{(r)}\| \sum_{i=1}^r \int_x^{\frac{i}{n}} \left(\frac{i}{n} - s\right)^{r-1} \phi^{-r}(s) ds \\ &\leq \frac{C}{n^r} \|w\phi^r f^{(r)}\|. \end{aligned}$$

Thus $I \leq C \|w\phi^r f^{(r)}\|$. So we get $I_2 \leq C \|w\phi^r f^{(r)}\|$. Above all, we have

$$|w(x)\phi^r(x)F_n^{(r)}(x)| \leq C \|w\phi^r f^{(r)}\|. \quad \square$$

Lemma 3.4. If $f \in W_\phi^r$, $\alpha, \beta > 0$, then

$$(3.6) \quad |w(x)(f(x) - L_r(f, x))|_{[0, \frac{2}{n}]} \leq C \left(\frac{\phi_n(x)}{\sqrt{n}\phi(x)}\right)^r \|w\phi^r f^{(r)}\|.$$

$$(3.7) \quad |w(x)(f(x) - R_r(f, x))|_{[1-\frac{2}{n}, 1]} \leq C \left(\frac{\delta_n(x)}{\sqrt{n}\phi(x)}\right)^r \|w\phi^r f^{(r)}\|.$$

Proof. By Taylor expansion, we have

$$(3.8) \quad f\left(\frac{i}{n}\right) = \sum_{u=0}^{r-1} \frac{\left(\frac{i}{n} - x\right)^u}{u!} f^{(u)}(x) + \frac{1}{(r-1)!} \int_x^{\frac{i}{n}} \left(\frac{i}{n} - s\right)^{r-1} f^{(r)}(s) ds,$$

It follows from (3.8) and the identities

$$\sum_{i=1}^{r-1} \binom{i}{n}^v l_i(x) = Cx^v, \quad v = 0, 1, \dots, r.$$

we have

$$\begin{aligned} L_r(f, x) &= \sum_{i=1}^r \sum_{u=0}^{r-1} \frac{(\frac{i}{n} - x)^u}{u!} f^{(u)}(x) l_i(x) + \frac{1}{(r-1)!} \sum_{i=1}^r l_i(x) \int_x^{\frac{i}{n}} (\frac{i}{n} - s)^{r-1} f^{(r)}(s) ds \\ &= f(x) + \sum_{u=1}^{r-1} f^{(u)}(x) \left(\sum_{v=0}^u C_u^v (-x)^{u-v} \sum_{i=1}^r \binom{i}{n}^v l_i(x) \right) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{(r-1)!} \sum_{i=1}^r l_i(x) \int_x^{\frac{i}{n}} (\frac{i}{n} - s)^{r-1} f^{(r)}(s) ds, \end{aligned}$$

Which implies that

$$w(x)|f(x) - L_r(f, x)| = \frac{1}{(r-1)!} w(x) \sum_{i=1}^r l_i(x) \int_x^{\frac{i}{n}} (\frac{i}{n} - s)^{r-1} f^{(r)}(s) ds,$$

Since $|l_i(x)| \leq C$ for $x \in [0, \frac{2}{n}]$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, r$.

It follows from $\frac{|\frac{i}{n} - s|^{r-1}}{w(s)} \leq \frac{|\frac{i}{n} - x|^{r-1}}{w(x)}$, s between $\frac{i}{n}$ and x , then

$$\begin{aligned} w(x)|f(x) - L_r(f, x)| &\leq Cw(x) \sum_{i=1}^r \int_x^{\frac{i}{n}} (\frac{i}{n} - s)^{r-1} |f^{(r)}(s)| ds \\ &\leq C \frac{\phi^r(x)}{\phi^r(x)} \|w\phi^r f^{(r)}\| \sum_{i=1}^r \int_x^{\frac{i}{n}} (\frac{i}{n} - s)^{r-1} \phi^{-r}(s) ds \\ &\leq C \frac{\delta_n^r(x)}{\phi^r(x)} \|w\phi^r f^{(r)}\| \sum_{i=1}^r \int_x^{\frac{i}{n}} (\frac{i}{n} - s)^{r-1} \phi^{-r}(s) ds \\ &\leq C \left(\frac{\delta_n(x)}{\sqrt{n}\phi(x)} \right)^r \|w\phi^r f^{(r)}\|. \end{aligned}$$

The proof of (3.7) can be done similarly. □

Lemma 3.5. ([13]) For every $\alpha, \beta > 0$, we have

$$(3.9) \quad \|wB_{n,r-1}^*(f)\| \leq C\|wf\|.$$

Lemma 3.6. ([17]) Let $\min\{\beta(0), \beta(1)\} \geq \frac{1}{2}$, then $r \in N$, $0 < t < \frac{1}{8r}$ and

$\frac{rt}{2} < x < 1 - \frac{rt}{2}$, we have

$$(3.10) \quad \int_{-\frac{t}{2}}^{\frac{t}{2}} \dots \int_{-\frac{t}{2}}^{\frac{t}{2}} \phi^{-r}(x + \sum_{k=1}^r u_k) du_1 \dots du_r \leq Ct^r \phi^{-r}(x).$$

Lemma 3.7. ([10]) Let $\alpha, \beta > 0$, for any $f \in C_w$, we have

$$(3.11) \quad \|wB_{n,r-1}^{*(r)}(f)\| \leq Cn^r \|wf\|.$$

4. Proof of Theorems

4.1. Proof of Theorem 2.1. When $f \in C_w, \min\{\beta(0), \beta(1)\} \geq \frac{1}{2}$, we discuss it as follows:

Case 1. If $0 \leq \varphi(x) \leq \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}$, by (3.11), we have

$$(4.1) \quad |w(x)\phi^r(x)B_{n,r-1}^{*(r)}(f,x)| = C\phi^r(x) \frac{\phi^r(x)}{\phi^r(x)} |w(x)B_{n,r-1}^{*(r)}(f,x)| \leq Cn^{\frac{r}{2}} \|wf\|.$$

Case 2. If $\varphi(x) > \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |B_{n,r-1}^{*(r)}(f,x)| &= |B_{n,r-1}^{(r)}(F_n,x)| \\ &\leq (\varphi^2(x))^{-r} \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} \sum_{j=0}^r Q_j(x,n_i) C_i(n) n_i^j \sum_{k=0}^{n_i} |(x - \frac{k}{n_i})^j F_n(\frac{k}{n_i})| p_{n_i,k}(x), \end{aligned}$$

By [5], we have

$$Q_j(x,n_i) = (n_i x(1-x))^{\lfloor \frac{r-j}{2} \rfloor}, \text{ and } (\varphi^2(x))^{-r} Q_j(x,n_i) n_i^j \leq C(n_i/\varphi^2(x))^{\frac{r+j}{2}}.$$

So

$$(4.2) \quad \begin{aligned} &|w(x)\phi^r(x)B_{n,r-1}^{*(r)}(f,x)| \\ &\leq Cw(x)\phi^r(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} \sum_{j=0}^r \left(\frac{n_i}{\varphi^2(x)}\right)^{\frac{r+j}{2}} \sum_{k=0}^{n_i} |(x - \frac{k}{n_i})^j F_n(\frac{k}{n_i})| p_{n_i,k}(x) \\ &\leq Cw(x)\phi^r(x) \|wf\| \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} \sum_{j=0}^r \left(\frac{n_i}{\varphi^2(x)}\right)^{\frac{r+j}{2}} \left\{ \sum_{k=0}^{n_i} (x - \frac{k}{n_i})^{2j} \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ &\quad \left\{ \sum_{k=0}^{n_i} w^{-2} \left(\frac{k}{n_i}\right) p_{n_i,k}(x) \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ &\leq Cn^{\frac{r}{2}} \|wf\|. \end{aligned}$$

It follows from combining with (4.1) and (4.2) that the theorem is proved. $\square$

4.2. Proof of Theorem 2.2. When $f \in W_\phi^r$, by [5], we have

$$(4.3) \quad B_{n,r-1}^{(r)}(F_n,x) = \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} C_i(n) n_i^r \sum_{k=0}^{n_i-r} \overset{\rightarrow}{\Delta}_{\frac{1}{n_i}}^r F_n\left(\frac{k}{n_i}\right) p_{n_i-r,k}(x).$$

If $0 < k < n_i - r$, we have

$$(4.4) \quad \left| \overrightarrow{\Delta}_{\frac{1}{n_i}}^r F_n\left(\frac{k}{n_i}\right) \right| \leq C n_i^{-r+1} \int_0^{\frac{x}{n_i}} |F_n^{(r)}\left(\frac{k}{n_i} + u\right)| du,$$

If $k = 0$, we have

$$(4.5) \quad \left| \overrightarrow{\Delta}_{\frac{1}{n_i}}^r F_n(0) \right| \leq C \int_0^{\frac{x}{n_i}} u^{r-1} |F_n^{(r)}(u)| du,$$

Similarly

$$(4.6) \quad \left| \overrightarrow{\Delta}_{\frac{1}{n_i}}^r F_n\left(\frac{n_i - r}{n_i}\right) \right| \leq C n_i^{-r+1} \int_{1-\frac{x}{n_i}}^1 (1-u)^{\frac{x}{n_i}} |F_n^{(r)}(u)| du.$$

By (4.3)-(4.6), we have

$$(4.7) \quad \begin{aligned} & |w(x)\phi^r(x)B_{n,r-1}^{*(r)}(f, x)| \\ & \leq C w(x)\phi^r(x) \|w\phi^r F_n^{(r)}\| \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} \sum_{k=0}^{n_i-r} (w\phi^r)^{-1}\left(\frac{k^*}{n_i}\right) p_{n_i-r,k}(x), \end{aligned}$$

If $k^* = 1$ for $k = 0$, $k^* = n_i - r - 1$ for $k = n_i - r$ and $k^* = k$ or $1 < k < n_i - r$.

By (3.1), we have

$$\sum_{k=0}^{n_i-r} (w\phi^r)^{-1}\left(\frac{k^*}{n_i}\right) p_{n_i-r,k}(x) \leq C (w\phi^r)^{-1}(x).$$

which combining with (4.7) give

$$|w(x)\phi^r(x)B_{n,r-1}^{*(r)}(f, x)| \leq C \|w\phi^r f^{(r)}\|. \square$$

Combining with the theorem 2.1 and theorem 2.2, we can obtain

Corollary. For any $\alpha, \beta > 0$, $0 \leq \lambda \leq 1$, we have

$$(4.8) \quad |w(x)\varphi^{r\lambda}(x)B_{n,r-1}^{*(r)}(f, x)| \leq \begin{cases} C n^{r/2} \{ \max\{n^{r(1-\lambda)/2}, \varphi^{r(\lambda-1)}(x)\} \|wf\|, & f \in C_w, \\ C \|w\varphi^{r\lambda} f^{(r)}\|, & f \in W_{w,\lambda}^r. \end{cases}$$

4.3 Proof of Theorem 2.3.

4.3.1. *The direct theorem.* We know

$$(4.9) \quad F_n(t) = F_n(x) + F_n'(t)(t-x) + \dots + \frac{1}{(r-1)!} \int_x^t (t-u)^{r-1} f^{(r)}(u) du,$$

$$(4.10) \quad B_{n,r-1}((\cdot-x)^k, x) = 0, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, r-1.$$

According to the definition of W_ϕ^r , for any $g \in W_\phi^r$, we have $B_{n,r-1}^*(g, x) = B_{n,r-1}(G_n(g), x)$, and $w(x)|G_n(x) - B_{n,r-1}(G_n, x)| = w(x)|B_{n,r-1}(R_r(G_n, t, x), x)|$,

thereof $R_r(G_n, t, x) = \int_x^t (t-u)^{r-1} G_n^{(r)}(u) du$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} w(x)|G_n(x) - B_{n,r-1}(G_n, x)| &\leq C \|w\phi^r G_n^{(r)}\| w(x) B_{n,r-1}\left(\int_x^t \frac{|t-u|^{r-1}}{w(u)\phi^r(u)} du, x\right) \\ &\leq C \|w\phi^r G_n^{(r)}\| w(x) \left(B_{n,r-1}\left(\int_x^t \frac{|t-u|^{r-1}}{\phi^{2r}(u)} du, x\right)\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ &\quad \left(B_{n,r-1}\left(\int_x^t \frac{|t-u|^{r-1}}{w^2(u)} du, x\right)\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}. \end{aligned} \tag{4.11}$$

also

$$\int_x^t \frac{|t-u|^{r-1}}{\phi^{2r}(u)} du \leq C \frac{|t-x|^r}{\phi^{2r}(x)}, \quad \int_x^t \frac{|t-u|^{r-1}}{w^2(u)} du \leq \frac{|t-x|^r}{w^2(x)}. \tag{4.12}$$

By (3.2), (3.3) and (4.12), we have

$$\begin{aligned} w(x)|G_n(x) - B_{n,r-1}(G_n, x)| &\leq C \|w\phi^r G_n^{(r)}\| \phi^{-r}(x) B_{n,r-1}(|t-x|^r, x) \\ &\leq C n^{-\frac{r}{2}} \frac{\varphi^r(x)}{\phi^r(x)} \|w\phi^r G_n^{(r)}\| \\ &\leq C n^{-\frac{r}{2}} \frac{\delta_n^r(x)}{\phi^r(x)} \|w\phi^r G_n^{(r)}\| \\ &= C \left(\frac{\delta_n(x)}{\sqrt{n}\phi(x)}\right)^r \|w\phi^r G_n^{(r)}\|. \end{aligned} \tag{4.13}$$

By (3.6), (3.7) and (4.13), when $g \in W_\phi^r$, then

$$\begin{aligned} w(x)|g(x) - B_{n,r-1}^*(g, x)| &\leq w(x)|g(x) - G_n(g, x)| + w(x)|G_n(g, x) - B_{n,r-1}^*(g, x)| \\ &\leq |w(x)(g(x) - L_r(g, x))|_{[0, \frac{2}{n}]} + |w(x)(g(x) - R_r(g, x))|_{[1-\frac{2}{n}, 1]} \\ &\quad + C \left(\frac{\delta_n(x)}{\sqrt{n}\phi(x)}\right)^r \|w\phi^r G_n^{(r)}\| \\ &\leq C \left(\frac{\delta_n(x)}{\sqrt{n}\phi(x)}\right)^r \|w\phi^r g^{(r)}\|. \end{aligned} \tag{4.14}$$

For $f \in C_w$, we choose proper $g \in W_\phi^r$, by (3.9) and (4.14), then

$$\begin{aligned} w(x)|f(x) - B_{n,r-1}^*(f, x)| &\leq w(x)|f(x) - g(x)| + w(x)|B_{n,r-1}^*(f - g, x)| \\ &\quad + w(x)|g(x) - B_{n,r-1}^*(g, x)| \\ &\leq C(\|w(f - g)\| + \left(\frac{\delta_n(x)}{\sqrt{n}\phi(x)}\right)^r \|w\phi^r g^{(r)}\|) \\ &\leq C\omega_\phi^r\left(f, \frac{\delta_n(x)}{\sqrt{n}\phi(x)}\right)_w. \square \end{aligned}$$

4.3.2. The inverse theorem. We define the weighted main-part modulus fo $D = R_+$ by(see [5])

$$\Omega_\phi^r(C, f, t)_w = \sup_{0 < h \leq t} \|w \Delta_{h\phi}^r f\|_{[Ch^*, \infty]},$$

$$\Omega_\phi^r(1, f, t)_w = \Omega_\phi^r(f, t)_w.$$

The main-part K -functional is given by

$$K_{r,\phi}(f, t^r)_w = \sup_{0 < h \leq t} \inf_g \{ \|w(f - g)\|_{[Ch^*, \infty]} + t^r \|w \phi^r g^{(r)}\|_{[Ch^*, \infty]}, g^{(r-1)} \in A.C.((Ch^*, \infty)) \}.$$

By [5], we have

$$(4.15) \quad C^{-1} \Omega_\phi^r(f, t)_w \leq \omega_\phi^r(f, t)_w \leq C \int_0^t \frac{\Omega_\phi^r(f, \tau)_w}{\tau} d\tau,$$

$$(4.16) \quad C^{-1} K_{r,\phi}(f, t^r)_w \leq \Omega_\phi^r(f, t)_w \leq C K_{r,\phi}(f, t^r)_w.$$

Proof. Let $\delta > 0$, we choose proper g so that

$$(4.17) \quad \|w(f - g)\| \leq C \Omega_\phi^r(f, \delta)_w, \quad \|w \phi^r g^{(r)}\| \leq C \delta^{-r} \Omega_\phi^r(f, \delta)_w.$$

For $r \in N$, $0 < t < \frac{1}{8r}$ and $\frac{rt}{2} < x < 1 - \frac{rt}{2}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |w(x) \Delta_{h\phi}^r f(x)| &\leq |w(x) \Delta_{h\phi}^r (f(x) - B_{n,r-1}^*(f, x))| + |w(x) \Delta_{h\phi}^r B_{n,r-1}^*(f - g, x)| \\ &\quad + |w(x) \Delta_{h\phi}^r B_{n,r-1}^*(g, x)| \\ &\leq \sum_{j=0}^r C_r^j \left(n^{-\frac{1}{2}} \frac{\delta_n(x + (\frac{r}{2} - j)h\phi(x))}{\phi(x + (\frac{r}{2} - j)h\phi(x))} \right)^{\alpha_0} \\ &\quad + \int_{-\frac{h\phi(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\phi(x)}{2}} \cdots \int_{-\frac{h\phi(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\phi(x)}{2}} w(x) B_{n,r-1}^{*(r)}(f - g, x + \sum_{k=1}^r u_k) du_1 \cdots du_r \\ &\quad + \int_{-\frac{h\phi(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\phi(x)}{2}} \cdots \int_{-\frac{h\phi(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\phi(x)}{2}} w(x) B_{n,r-1}^{*(r)}(g, x + \sum_{k=1}^r u_k) du_1 \cdots du_r \end{aligned}$$

$$(4.18) \quad \quad \quad := J_1 + J_2 + J_3.$$

Obviously

$$(4.19) \quad J_1 \leq C(n^{-\frac{1}{2}} \phi^{-1}(x) \delta_n(x))^{\alpha_0}.$$

By (3.11) and (4.17), we have

$$\begin{aligned} J_2 &\leq C n^r \|w(f - g)\| \int_{-\frac{h\phi(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\phi(x)}{2}} \cdots \int_{-\frac{h\phi(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\phi(x)}{2}} du_1 \cdots du_r \\ &\leq C n^r h^r \phi^r(x) \|w(f - g)\| \\ (4.20) \quad &\leq C n^r h^r \phi^r(x) \Omega_\phi^r(f, \delta)_w. \end{aligned}$$

By the first inequality of (4.8), we let $\lambda = 1$, and (3.10) as well as (4.17), then

$$\begin{aligned}
 J_2 &\leq Cn^{\frac{r}{2}} \|w(f - g)\| \int_{-\frac{h\phi(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\phi(x)}{2}} \cdots \int_{-\frac{h\phi(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\phi(x)}{2}} \varphi^{-r}(x + \sum_{k=1}^r u_k) du_1 \cdots du_r \\
 &\leq Cn^{\frac{r}{2}} h^r \phi^r(x) \varphi^{-r}(x) \|w(f - g)\| \\
 (4.21) \quad &\leq Cn^{\frac{r}{2}} h^r \phi^r(x) \varphi^{-r}(x) \Omega_\phi^r(f, \delta)_w.
 \end{aligned}$$

By the second inequality of (3.10) and (4.17), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 J_3 &\leq C \|w\phi^r g^{(r)}\| w(x) \int_{-\frac{h\phi(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\phi(x)}{2}} \cdots \int_{-\frac{h\phi(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\phi(x)}{2}} w^{-1}(x + \sum_{k=1}^r u_k) \phi^{-r}(x + \sum_{k=1}^r u_k) du_1 \cdots du_r \\
 &\leq Ch^r \|w\phi^r g^{(r)}\| \\
 (4.22) \quad &\leq Ch^r \delta^{-r} \Omega_\phi^r(f, \delta)_w.
 \end{aligned}$$

Now, by (4.18)-(4.22), there exists $M > 0$ so that

$$\begin{aligned}
 |w(x) \Delta_{h\phi}^r f(x)| &\leq C \left((n^{-\frac{1}{2}} \frac{\delta_n(x)}{\phi(x)})^{\alpha_0} \right. \\
 &+ \min\{n^{\frac{r}{2}} \frac{\phi^r(x)}{\varphi^r(x)}, n^r \phi^r(x)\} h^r \Omega_\phi^r(f, \delta)_w + h^r \delta^{-r} \Omega_\phi^r(f, \delta)_w \\
 &\leq C \left((n^{-\frac{1}{2}} \frac{\delta_n(x)}{\phi(x)})^{\alpha_0} \right. \\
 &+ h^r M^r (n^{-\frac{1}{2}} \frac{\varphi(x)}{\phi(x)} + n^{-\frac{1}{2}} \frac{n^{-1/2}}{\phi(x)})^{-r} \Omega_\phi^r(f, \delta)_w + h^r \delta^{-r} \Omega_\phi^r(f, \delta)_w \\
 &\leq C \left((n^{-\frac{1}{2}} \frac{\delta_n(x)}{\phi(x)})^{\alpha_0} \right. \\
 &\left. + h^r M^r (n^{-\frac{1}{2}} \frac{\delta_n(x)}{\phi(x)})^{-r} \Omega_\phi^r(f, \delta)_w + h^r \delta^{-r} \Omega_\phi^r(f, \delta)_w \right).
 \end{aligned}$$

When $n \geq 2$, we have

$$n^{-\frac{1}{2}} \delta_n(x) < (n - 1)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \delta_{n-1}(x) \leq \sqrt{2} n^{-\frac{1}{2}} \delta_n(x),$$

Choosing proper $x, \delta, n \in N$, so that

$$n^{-\frac{1}{2}} \frac{\delta_n(x)}{\phi(x)} \leq \delta < (n - 1)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \frac{\delta_{n-1}(x)}{\phi(x)},$$

Therefore

$$|w(x) \Delta_{h\phi}^r f(x)| \leq C \{ \delta^{\alpha_0} + h^r \delta^{-r} \Omega_\phi^r(f, \delta)_w \}.$$

By Borens-Lorentz lemma, we get

$$(4.23) \quad \Omega_{\phi}^r(f, t)_w \leq Ct^{\alpha_0}.$$

So, by (4.15) and (4.23), we get

$$\omega_{\phi}^r(f, t)_w \leq C \int_0^t \frac{\Omega_{\phi}^r(f, \tau)_w}{\tau} d\tau = C \int_0^t \tau^{\alpha_0-1} d\tau = Ct^{\alpha_0}. \quad \square$$

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